

IN THE MAKING: MATERIAL AND IMMATERIAL TRANSFORMATIONS IN COLOMBIAN INDIGENOUS COMMUNITIES

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the analytical status of “hybrid” material transformations that flourish in the indigenous communities of Vichada, Colombia, building on previous relevant work in the area of creativity and value perception. It suggests that the approach to materiality as “becoming” rather than “being” reveals a strategy of creation and recreation of value and identity through the production of meaningful connections in a changing environment. This creation of value is achieved through action, and more specifically by means of the act of making, revealing a selective and active approach towards the material world.

KEYWORDS: *material culture, creativity, appropriation, transformation, making*

INTRODUCTION

Material culture crafted by indigenous people in Vichada, Colombia is being continually modified in response to the changing environment. Women squeeze bitter cassava turning it into artefacts made of natural fibres or packaging tape; kids run around the communities playing with cars made from motor oil bottles; plastic chairs are sown together to keep them from falling apart; and a caiman skin merges with a metal structure to become a chair. These transformations challenge the understanding of tradition and continuity and value creativity and the production of meaningful connections.

This paper will focus on a series of objects, interventions, modifications and translations that flourish in indigenous communities in Vichada. These materializations are made up not only of natural resources, but also of industrial materials that have become accessible to the communities as a result of urban expansion. ‘New’ materials acquire meaning in their interaction with people, and specifically through the act of making and using, becoming part of their daily communal lives. It is a process of appropriation (Schneider, 2006), whereby materials are selectively incorporated and transformed acquiring value in the new compositions.

Making, as a traditional way of satisfying needs, constitutes not only a specific approach to the environment and a physical and symbolic practice, but also results in a materialization that presents itself as a frozen image of relations. The materiality of making represents a pause in the flow, an

objectification that has the ability to speak in a unique way (Tilley2006:62), which permits the observer, or we may say the listener, to unravel the web behind it. By studying the traces of relations in the process of making, and the use of resources in a changing environment, one can understand how these transformations come into being and how they are valued in their specific context.

LITERATURE REVIEW: CREATIVE TRANSFORMATIONS

This paper will examine the analytical status of material transformations in the everyday communal life of indigenous people in Vichada. Pivotal to this is the body of literature surrounding creativity as an essential element in the processes of transformation of the material world. Additionally, it is important to take into account the discussions around the relationship between people and things and to explore the literature on hybridity as a way of understanding what things (and people) are made of.

Engaging with things from the perspective of making brings questions that go beyond materiality to discover their more intricate conformation, both material and immaterial. Ingold (2007, 2012) advocates for the dematerialization of materiality, looking to move toward an *ecology of materials* where the attention focuses on the flows of materials that give rise to the things themselves. Similarly, Holbraad (2011) proposes a prag-

matological model that values material properties as generators of conceptual affordances that can set the terms for the understanding of things.

These perspectives move away from the ontological distinction between subjects and objects, which places the human as the centre of the system of relations. Within this ontology, Miller's (2005) approach is based on the dialectical process of objectification, where things, through their interaction with people, contribute to the definition of the latter. However, in this specific relationship, things can be said to be already made physically and only in the making symbolically. As Appadurai (1986) affirms, things have a social life and they are modified as they move and interact with people; however, what is considered malleable is their meaning more than their material composition. The status of things then, has been discussed both in terms of their wholeness and of their configuration resulting in different levels of understanding of their interaction. By looking at objects in the making, but moving forward to understand their further relation to the users, who, in this case, are commonly the same makers, one can begin to unravel the multiple significances of things and make connections between these levels.

The material and immaterial transformation of things is the result of a creative process; therefore, creativity can be considered an important concept to analyse as a strategy of engagement with things and materials. To understand this concept, Leach (2004) explains that there is not just one creativity, but modes of creativity that are shaped by different contexts. Appropriative creativity is the materialization of an intellectual input, which aims for an economic profit, while distributive creativity goes beyond the tangible result to value the making of connections (see Levi-Strauss, 1966). Ingold and Hallam (2007) explain the concept in terms of the on-going process of life. It is not just the specific instantiation of novel creation (see Liep, 2001), but a process of adaptation that not only produces things, but also transforms the people involved. Creativity then, is a concept that links people and things, and can allow us to explore the connections between the elements that make up their interaction.

By decomposing the whole into its constituent parts and the way that they are attached to each other through the creative process, one begins to understand both people and things in a different way. The relational make-up of events reveals an inherent hybridity behind every complete form (García Canclini, 1997; Amselle, 1998; Baron, 2011; Clifford, 2002; Schneider, 2006). To go beyond the search for pure original forms, Amselle (1998) proposes to think in terms of an originary syncretism, which results from a constant practice of negotiation of identity. This process is conceptualized by Schneider (2006) in terms of appropriation. According to him, appropriation is a strategy for identity construction whereby a subject uses an external element and invests it with meaning in a new composition; altering both the element and himself. It is a dynamic process where all of the elements involved are active in their mutual constitution, and so, their existence depends on this encounter.

RESEARCH

The data presented in this paper was collected during two years' of fieldwork in indigenous communities in Vichada, Colombia, while working with the NGO *Fundación Etnollano*.² I joined the sustainable production team as a design advisor, working with groups of indigenous artisans and helping them develop sustainable craft processes based on their traditional knowledge. During this time, I studied the way that the communities relate to their material culture, gaining an understanding of their approach to making and resources. Even though my work was related to traditional crafts, I began to observe the way that other more "hybrid" creations were made and used within the communities and began to study these covert creations.

The research was undertaken mainly through participant observation and informal conversations. I conducted interviews with 5 artisans from 3 communities with different ethnic backgrounds (*Piaroa*, *Sikuani* and *Amorúa*), regarding the alternative transformations in opposition to what they call traditional crafts. I used photo elicitation, with images of a collection of objects from the three communities (*Cachicamo*, *Joval* and *Guáripa*) in order to talk about the stories of how they came to be and the role that they play within the communities.

This paper unravels the stories, meanings and connections that develop around 4 hybrid objects, which represent many other instances present within the communities. These examples were selected not only because of the willingness of the creators and users to discuss their existence, but also because of the objects' capacity to represent important characteristics that can be extrapolated to other cases of hybrid transformation.

Case 1: Material Affordances: The Plastic Sebucán

The *sebucán* is one of the most important elements to prepare *bitter cassava*³. It is used for squeezing the poison out of the root, to make it edible. It has a specific weaving pattern that

1 2010-2012

2 The NGO, *Fundación Etnollano*, has been linked to these lands since it was founded in 1985, working towards the improvement of the quality of life of indigenous, rural and marginal communities. To achieve this aim, they work on projects related to health, environmental and ethno-education, protection of cultural heritage and sustainable production. For further information see www.etnollano.org

3 Bitter cassava is one of the basic plants cultivated by the indigenous people of Vichada. This root is highly nutritious and hence, an important part of their daily diet. There is a rich material culture around bitter cassava, which responds to a particular way of cultivation, preparation and cooking. The preparation of this plant for consumption is very important because the root itself, without the proper process, is poisonous to both human beings and animals.

Figure 1. *Sebucán* made of plastic packaging tape and *tirita* in the community of *Cachicamo*. Image taken by the author.

tightens its contents as it is pulled in order to extract all of the liquid from the grated cassava⁴.

In the community of *Cachicamo*⁵, the traditional *sebucán* made from *tirita*, a natural fibre, is hanging next to one made from green plastic packaging tape. This object maintains its traditional shape and use but has undergone a material translation. Even though the plastic *sebucán* works well and lasts longer than the other, it does not necessarily replace the original object, which provides a tighter squeeze.

Packaging tape from the remains of the packages of different products transported from the cities is a material that is often found in urban centres. It is considered trash within the urban context; however, as Strassler (1999) affirms, “What counts as trash has always depended on who is counting” (p.289). Thompson (1979) explains that the way that we act towards an object depends on a categorization, which is necessarily social. According to him, objects are divided into three categories: durable, transient and rubbish. The first two make up the overt or visible part of the system and they differ in terms of their lifespan and value. The durable category is characterized by the ability to acquire value in time and has an (ideally) infinite lifespan, while the objects within the transient category lose value in time and have a finite lifespan (Ibid). Rubbish, on the other hand, conforms the covert or invisible part of the system being value-less. This third category becomes important for the dynamics of the whole system because it is located in a region of flexibility that is not subject to the same control mechanisms. Hence, it is possible for rubbish to be transferred into one of the overt categories, arising as a potentially temporary and mutable category that can ac-

quire value and be re-categorized through an act of discovery (Ibid).

The packaging tape falls into the transient category whilst in use in the urban context, as soon as the package is unpacked, the tape enters the rubbish category completely losing its value. However, once it is recognized by the indigenous people and used to weave a *sebucán*, it re-enters the transient category starting a new lifespan.

The plastic *sebucán* represents a transfer between categories, changing the way that people act around this specific material. In the eyes of the indigenous people of *Cachicamo*, packaging tape is never rubbish, for they recognize its characteristics and appreciate the material in relation to what it can become. This sensitivity in terms of materials and their properties promotes a diminishment of the rubbish category and reveals a cyclical view of things fostered by continual transformations.

These transformations are triggered by the affordances of things. The term affordance, coined by Gibson (1986), refers to what the material, in this case, has to offer to the person that engages with it (Ibid p.127). Knappet (2004) explains the concept in terms of relationality, whereby the affordances come not from the object or from the person, but from the situation of encounter (Ibid p. 46).

If one considers the packaging tape and its dissimilar categorization in the urban and indigenous contexts, one can begin to understand how the perception of affordances promotes action, and through action, value is created or destroyed. The packaging tape, by having similar characteristics to the natural fibre used to make a *sebucán*, affords weaving to those sensitive to material properties, triggering a creative process that ends up changing its categorization and entering the realm of elements available for transformation.

Case 2: Making Connections: The *Makibü* Chair

There is a remarkable diversity of chairs in the community of *Joval*⁶, which have all been transformed and adapted. The *Makibü* chair is a particularly interesting example; it stands out for being aesthetically different although it is considered to be a chair like any other. It does not have a particular owner, it does not signify a hierarchical position, as Elvira⁷ explains, “I have it there and everyone sits on it.” Listening to the story of how it came to be, one realizes that it is just one option out of many, the result of a successful trial in the

4 Men normally make this artefact; it is one of the craft activities that any man must master in order to be able to marry. He must provide her with the necessary baskets for their day-to-day life and she, on the other hand, is in charge of preparing the food using these artefacts.

5 The community of *Cachicamo* is a *Piaroa* community located in the *Resguardo Cachicamo* in the lower Orinoco River, near the city of Puerto Ayacucho in Venezuela.

6 The community of *Joval* is located in the *Resguardo la Hormiga*, north of *Cachicamo* and closer to the urban centre of Puerto Carreño in Colombia

7 Elvira is the oldest woman of the community, and mother and grandmother to many of the community members and leader of the group of artisans of *Joval*.

8 Elvira explains that there are many *Makibü* in the nearby rivers, but the men do not kill them everyday. “They are forbidden animals”, she says, not traditionally but by the local authorities that believe they must be protected. For this reason, the indigenous men hunt them once in a while and use them for communal consumption only.

FIGURE 2: Makibü chair in the community of Joval Image taken by the author

creative flow that has survived because of its efficiency within the specific context.

Makibü is the Sikuani word for a type of caiman that lives in the nearby rivers which is killed and eaten by the people.⁸ The story of the chair is quite simple; the men went out fishing and caught a *Makibü*, they took the meat and left the skin to rot. But one of the fishermen saw the skin laying there and had an idea; he was not looking for a way to use the skin, he did not particularly need a chair, he just remembered the existence of the metal structure and realized that the shape of these two different materialities could fit together in an interesting way. He decided to take the skin with him to the community and give his idea a try. It worked, and so, they began using this newly created chair. It was a good chair; made from available resources and comfortable. Seeing that there were several metal structures lying around the community⁹, the fisherman decided that he could make another chair. So the next time that he caught a *Makibü*, he carefully took the skin off and let it dry. However Elvira remembers that one of the dogs took the skin and destroyed it, so he gave up on his idea.

The *Makibü* chair materializes a connection between natural resources and industrial materials. The fisherman acts as a bricoleur, who uses different elements found within his environment and relates them in a specific way (Lévi-Strauss, 1966). As Lévi-Strauss explains, “The decision as to what to put in each place also depends on the possibility of putting a different element there instead, so that each choice which is made will involve a complete reorganization of the structure, which will never be the same as one vaguely imag-

9 Probably remains from chairs received as donations or from the nearby school or even bought by one of the community members in Puerto Carreño.

ined nor as some other which might have been preferred to it” (Lévi-Strauss, 1966 p.19). The metal structure could have been connected to different materials to make a chair (or even a different end), but the fisherman’s decision, in his relation to both the affordances of the materials and his environment, resulted in one possibility.

This materialization represents a relational potential that is realized in the world as an outcome of the creative flow. The interchangeability of elements depicted by Lévi-Strauss in his description of bricolage generates material structures that have weaker physical bonds between their components. This, in turn, ends up promoting the understanding of objects, not as fixed materialities, but as constructions, valuing the parts as much as the whole, and allowing these to become instruments for further action (Leach, 2004).

Following this conceptualization, the indigenous people’s approach to the environment and their daily practice is part of a creative flow that engenders their living conditions and allows them to move through time in a constant regeneration. Creativity appears as a way to cope with the encounter, promoting an inclusive approach towards the changing conditions of the environment. The appreciation of materials as “becoming” rather than “being”, and the inclusion of the new resources within their milieu as part of their field of action, allows them to interact within this particular context.

This understanding of the material world overturns the hylomorphic model of creation¹⁰ criticized by Ingold (2010) whereby the people impose form on materials, and opens up into an inverted approach. From this perspective and in relation to making, creativity is not about the objects that it is able to produce, but about the way that the maker and the materials interact and are modified by the act of making. This shifts the perspective from the result to the process of making, allowing to trace the transformations rather than to search for material and cultural stability (Ibid). The chair is a temporal object, which is able to fulfil a function as a whole; however, it will always be a composition that cannot only be taken apart, but also be made again in the same and many different ways.

Case 3: Revaluing Elements: The Toy Car

The boys from the Guáripa¹¹ community play with a very interesting toy: an empty motor oil bottle made into a car. With the intro-

10 “To create any thing, Aristotle reasoned, you have to bring together form (morphe) and matter (hyle). In the subsequent history of Western thought, this hylomorphic model of creation became ever more deeply embedded. But it also became increasingly unbalanced. Form came to be seen as imposed by an agent with a particular design in mind, while matter, thus rendered passive and inert, became that which was imposed upon.” (Ingold, 2010, p.92)

11 The community of Guáripa is located in the Resguardo Caño Guáripa, only a thirty-minute boat ride from the urban centre of Puerto Carreño. The Amorúa people were traditionally nomads; moving from one place to another has led them to become masters of adaptation.

duction of engines to the community, these bottles have become part of their environment, available resources waiting to be used.

In general, all of the components of this unique toy speak about the community and its relations, about the changes in their environment. The shape of the bottle resembles that of a car, which the children have seen either in the nearby urban centres or even just on television. The wheels are plastic bottle caps, of different shapes and sizes, collected either from visitors, home groceries, or in the urban centres. They are attached to the bottle with lollipop sticks, which are the remains of gifts commonly brought by visitors to the children of *Guáripa*. The car is thus an ensemble of different plastic disposable elements that only acquire value through action, when combined to create a coherent form.

The making process comes about through collaboration between the children and their fathers. The kids collect the different elements around the community and the men put the toys together. The territory where this car must travel is rocky, bumpy and steep, so the children have adapted a string, from their mothers' weaving fibres and tied it to a stick to be able to, tied to a stick, to be able to pull the car. As a result of their experience with the car in movement, they have decided to place stones inside it, giving it the necessary weight to prevent it from turning over.

This toy relates internal objects and concepts with external objects and concepts resulting in an objectification of a hybrid reality. It goes beyond the idea of an individual maker, to uncover the way in which community members, through their family relations, are involved together in the creation of material culture. The toy car, as an ensemble, is the result of a series of characteristics and events that are part of the lives of the indigenous people: the act of moving on motorboats, groceries brought from the urban centres, sweets given by visitors to the children, women weaving string bags, kids climbing on trees to get sticks, a community constructed on the rocks.

The use of elements considered as trash to make new compositions that serve a different purpose, has been categorized

as *recyclia* or third-world recycling (Dziedzic, 2008). This understanding of the objects focuses on the elements and their previous uses, making their new appreciation interesting for those who are familiar with the use and discarded of their components (Kratz, 1995). Kratz (1995) criticizes this approach, proposing to rethink the transformations from the maker's perspective instead of just admiring the irony of their existence. She affirms that people celebrate *recyclia*'s productivity and creativity, but few have analysed the conditions where these transformations arise (Ibid). Therefore, instead of grouping these objects in one external category, they can be used as a starting-point to analyse the culture where and for which they are produced (Coote, 2000).

At first sight, the existence of these objects in the community of *Guáripa*, signals what Cerny (1996) describes as the "ubiquitous intrusion of material modernity in even the remotest corners of the world" (Ibid p.12). However, when one realizes that this material modernity is selectively incorporated and transformed by the people of the community, intrusion does not seem like the appropriate term to characterize the interaction. It is a process of appropriation that transforms each of the elements giving them meaning in relation to the new composition. Seen in this light, the indigenous people of *Guáripa* are not passive observers of the 'intrusion' of modernity, but are engaged in an active transformation of their material environment.

This process of appropriation allows the transfer from rubbish to transient, through giving the materialities the possibility of becoming something else. As with the packaging tape and the metal structure, as soon as they acquire meaning within their specific context, the elements are re-categorized, modifying the actions that take place around them. Plastic motor oil bottles cease to be just containers that hold the oil necessary for the movement of the people outside of the community, they become potential toy cars that can promote the movement of the children within the community. Lollipop sticks afford the holding of candy as well as that of wheels, and plastic bottle caps are valued for their ability to roll on the rocks.

FIGURE 3: Motor oil bottle car in the community of *Guáripa* Image taken by the author

FIGURE 4: Reconstructed chair in the community of *Joval* Image taken by the author

Case 4: *Artefacts of Attachment: The Reconstructed Chair*

In the community of *Joval*, a chair that has been completely and proudly sewn up shows the scars that evidence its story. This reconstructed chair reveals an amazingly different understanding of materials and their characteristics; the broken plastic has been ingeniously sewn together with nylon thread, giving the object a new life. It integrates fishing materials, plastic and traditional sewing techniques in a very unexpected way.

As Strassler (1999) affirms, “repair ideas come more easily to people who make things” (p.10). Their tactile understanding of objects goes beyond wholeness, to the properties of materials and their possibilities of transformation. Therefore, a broken object does not necessarily lose its value, but it becomes available for revaluation through the creative process. Objects made and used by the indigenous people in their daily lives are normally repaired to extend their lifespan. This mending process is different from other processes of transformation in that it prolongs the life of the object and so its specific purpose, instead of the life of the materials, beyond their configuration as objects. In other words, certain objects resist being transformed into something different, maintaining their integrity as objects for a longer time.

The story of this chair reveals a mending process, stimulated not by its functionality, but by the emotional significance tied to the object. The original plastic blue chair had been brought to the community from Puerto Carreño as a present to one of the men. His uncle, who lived in the urban centre, had earned enough money to buy a gift for him. He proudly brought the chair to the community; a plastic chair which would last longer than others, a chair that could get wet, be easily cleaned and resist exposure to outside conditions. Although this chair belonged to one specific man, it soon became used by all of the community members, like most of the objects present in *Joval*, which tend to move around from person to person. Some months later, the uncle died in an accident; this event modified the value of the chair completely. It changed from being just a chair to becoming the memory of a lost loved one; it acquired an emotional importance in the eyes of the nephew; a physical connection to an immaterial relation. But, the physical does not last as long as the emotional. The durability of plastic is threatened by long exposure to the sun, which crystalizes the material making it brittle.

Elvira remembers that the children broke the chair into many pieces, while playing with it on a sunny day. The nephew could not stand the idea of having his uncle’s chair shattered into pieces, so he began to sew. He took all of the pieces and put them together like a puzzle. He began by making holes with a warm nail on the edges of the broken plastic. He used the nails left from the construction of houses and the fire from the communal kitchen. He then decided to put it all together by using a nylon thread, a material used for fishing that proved to be more resistant than organic fibres. He spent a long time sewing the pieces together using the traditional cross pattern to make it stronger. “He was very patient,” recounts Elvira.

The time invested undertaking such a task, which clearly does not have a functional aim, shows a different appreciation of the creative process. As Sennett states, “The slowness of craft time serves as a source of satisfaction; practice beds in, making the skill one’s own” (Sennett, 2008 p.295). The craft process therefore acquires value in itself through the effect that it has on the people involved.

The transformation of things not only responds to a material curiosity that allows for the practical use of their physical properties in a particular way, but also to the immaterial meanings attached to the physical world. The malleability of materiality is contextually defined, and so, as Ingold (2000) states “The temporal rhythms of life are gradually built into the structural properties of things” (p.345). What seemed like an external object representative of the modern world, was transformed through interaction into a highly personalized metaphorical medium. The plastic chair, through its process of transformation (both of breaking and mending), objectifies the experience of a man living in the community of *Joval*.

CONCLUSIONS

The material culture of the indigenous communities of Vichada includes transformations that are the result of the encounter with the urban centres and the “modern” way of life. They evidence the effacement of barriers between these two worlds and a latent creativity that transforms the external into familiar compositions that adapt to a changing context. In this context, the act of making reasserts its position as the traditional way of transforming the properties of materials to favour the people in their daily practice. It is through the physical creation of things that people are able to cope with the encounter, creating and recreating their identity.

The possibility of transformation arises through the encounter between the indigenous people and the material world, and therefore it cannot be attributed to any of the two on their own, but to the more complex result of their moments of interaction. Making things for use composes a system that is entangled prior to any instantiation, strengthening the inherent interdependence. The relationship established between finished elements (subject and object) in the creation of value (Simmel, 1990), degrades into the mutual constitution of potentialities, modifying the pattern of action that takes place between them. From this perspective, value is created in action¹²; it results from the input of energy that transforms affordances into movements. It is the encounter between an indigenous person and a piece of packaging tape that produces a possibility, which leads to the action of weaving. Therefore, value is created not before or after action, but during the physical movement of transformation.

¹² Munn’s work describes a similar perspective whereby value emerges in action, yet her conceptualization of value is directly related to the making visible of the human capacity to act through concrete forms (Graeber, 2001 p.45), excluding the essential input of materiality as part of a mutually dependent system.

The understanding of things not as complete objects but partial processes (Ingold, 2012), allows the indigenous people of Vichada to recognize potential in all of the materialities that they encounter while encouraging them to be part of the subsequent transformation towards the creation of a beneficial flow of materials. These processes occur at the level of using, concurring with Miller's (1987) creative consumption and Appadurai's (1986) social life of things. However, they also dig deeper, modifying the most basic physical structures, which in turn change all of the subsequent interactions. If a poisonous root, lethal to human beings and animals, can become the basic food source of the indigenous people of Vichada, anything and everything is possible.

Bitter cassava, like other materialities in this indigenous context, does not depend on its wholeness to be evaluated by the people; if it were so, it would have been discarded as dangerous and eliminated from the possibilities of everyday life. By decomposing it into its most basic parts, the people have found a way to benefit from it, unleashing a process of transformation composed of multiple artefacts, which depend on other transformations in order to exist. It is easy to understand this process from the perspective of men and women transforming their surroundings, yet with a little effort one is also able to picture bitter cassava as the main character, transforming men and women (and their activities) for many generations. This reversed ontology uncovers the impact of materialities and their properties on the people, challenging the supremacy of the subject and depicting a more balanced system of interaction.

Within this system, creativity must necessarily be understood as an on-going process of transformation, which transcends the temporal material instantiations. Therefore, it becomes a concept, which cannot be easily pinned down as the action of a subject on an object, but that involves and demands a confluence of forces in movement. If people make things and things make people (if they can be distinguished in such a way), then neither of them has the required independence to be responsible for the creative act. Creativity does not arise from the person who weaves a plastic *sebucán*, it is the packaging tape discovered in the eyes of the indigenous, which affords the creative transformation, and such an act consequently creates a new *sebucán*; yet also a changed person, and a different packaging tape.¹³

The fisherman making the *Makibü* chair is not searching for a potential solution to a specific problem, he is free from the burden of execution and so, plunges into the domain of uncertainty and risk that encompasses any craft process (Adamson, 2011). What is accomplished then, is not the resulting chair, but the connection established and the possibilities that this connection may bring. As Levi-Strauss (1966) writes in his explanation of the relation between a woodpecker and a toothache, "The real question is not whether the touch of a woodpecker's beak does in fact cure toothache. It is rather whether there is

a point of view from which a woodpecker's beak and a man's tooth can be seen as 'going together'"(Ibid p.9).

In this sense, the *Makibü* skin merges with the metal structure as a feasible possibility, reflecting the potential connection between natural and industrial resources within the indigenous context. The consequent social life of the resulting object in the community endorses the viability of the connection, and in some cases, may result in the reproduction of the same or similar objects. The failed reproduction of the *Makibü* chair due to the intervention of a dog shows the lack of attachment to the material instantiation and the input of different forces in the creative process.

The toy car, on the other hand, exemplifies a successful process of reproduction of connections. The object is reproduced because of the availability of resources, which in the end, signal a reproduction of the social relations that bring these specific resources to the community. Therefore, the persistence of the toy car necessarily implies the movement of men on motorboats and a continual relation with the urban centres. The toy reveals the permeability between the rural and urban worlds on a material and immaterial level, becoming a metaphor for the indigenous reality.

Furthermore, it is an object that evolves with use, going through additional transformations that result from its interaction. The toy car is never finished; it grows with the children and their activities. Therefore it is an object that not only evidences the presence of elements coming from outside the community, but also shows the way that they interact with internal elements, composing a hybrid assembly.

If everything is made up of a combination of elements, what becomes interesting is not only recognizing hybridity, but also being able to decompose things to understand how they come to be and the effect that each one of those elements has through the process of becoming part of the composition. The combination of elements in the making must go through a process of appropriation (Schneider, 2006). It is not only about the materials at hand and how the external elements are digested from the inside in order for them to be able to interact and become part of the creative compositions, but it is also about the way in which the subjects involved in this process suffer their own transformations, re-defining their identities.

The material transformations that flourish in the indigenous communities of Vichada are not only an ingenious way of transforming industrial objects and materials into new compositions with renewed meanings and uses, but a strategy towards the understanding of the other and the construction of their own identity. In Puerto Carreño, a broken plastic chair quickly enters the rubbish category, while in *Joval*, it is transformed into a composition that challenges the passing of time by holding together, through devious means, what was meant to be apart. The reconstruction of the chair not only reveals a unique understanding of materials and their properties, but also the specific significance, attributed to the object through the process of appropriation. Appropriation then, is a modification

13 And one could go further to list the changes that these three modified forces bring about the people around them, their activities, the environment and therefore their culture.

of the physical and semantic structure of materialities, which in turn, modify the system that supports them, including the subject involved in the process. It is through this process that value is created in the indigenous communities of Vichada.

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